

ATHLETES OF SURKHANDARYO ARE IN THE UZBEKISTAN PARALYMPIC TEAM TEAM

Xasanov Ilyos To‘ychievich

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Associate Professor of Physical Culture Department

Abstract: This article contains information about the participation of the national team of Uzbekistan in the Paralympic sports competitions, the achievements and results of the representatives of our national team, and the conditions created for the Paralympic sports in our country. At the same time, information about Surkhandarya athletes who participated in the Paralympic sports competitions as part of our national team is presented, this article serves as one of the important sources for specialists and students of physical culture education.

Key words: Paralympics, system, national team, spiritually pure, intellectually mature, physically strong, mature, patriotic, courage, tenacity, Sprouts of Hope, Perfect Generation, Universiade.

Like all other fields in the world, the field of physical education and sports also educates the future generation of nations and peoples, i.e., the young generation of tomorrow, to be spiritually pure, mentally mature and physically strong and perfect in every way, while also improving the health of the population through physical education and sports. recognize as one of the main factors of strengthening. The countries of the world, along with educating the young generation to be physically fit and well-rounded, each country considers it one of the highest goals of physical education to raise its future generations as children who will serve their country with love and loyalty. They produce and implement their educational and educational tasks focusing on this.

In the chapter of the physical education system of Uzbekistan aimed at deciding the content of education for themselves in the educational institutions, there

is an article that the purpose of physical education in the education of the young generation is to raise the young generation to be fully perfect, worthy of the defense of the country. perhaps, in the sports competitions held in the world arenas in all kinds of sports, important tasks such as adequately protecting the honor of their homeland are being instilled in the minds of young people. Since the day we gained independence, athletes of our country, who have adopted their state symbols, are participating in Asian, World, Olympic and Paralympic sports competitions under the new national flag of their beloved homeland, Uzbekistan, and have been adequately protecting the honor of our homeland. is a great strength and a great honor for us. We can see the result of the state's attention and created conditions for our athletes who bravely defend the honor of our independent land and participate in the Olympic and Paralympic sports competitions in the example of the achievements of our athletes in the Olympic and Paralympic sports competitions.

"Alpomish and Barchinoy" special tests for people of all ages and sports competitions at all levels of educational institutions for general education school students in order to develop physical education and sports and introduce a healthy lifestyle in our country The sports competitions "Umid Nihollar", "Barkamol Avlod" for students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges and "Universiade" for students of higher educational institutions have been organized to introduce the young generation of this country to the world. it is possible to realize that they are growing up with a high goal in front of them. Because before athletes have the status of sportsmen, they first protect themselves and their family in the qualifiers in their regions, then their district and educational institutions in the regional sports competitions, and the honor of their regions in the Republican sports competitions. They grow up realizing how great a duty and task it is to raise them.

In the same way, we are glad that today there are many of our truly patriotic boys and girls who defended the honor of our country in sports competitions and raised the flag of our country to the top of the world arenas and forced the sports fans of the whole world to listen to the anthem of our country.

The result of our athletes who adequately defend the honor of our country at the Uzbekistan, Asian, World, Olympic and Paralympic sports competitions is a clear proof of our opinion. In particular, we can give an example of the achievements and bravery of our athletes who are the participants of the Paralympics, who have been defending the honor of our country.

At the 2004 XII Paralympic sports competitions held in Athens, Greece, where our representatives participated for the first time, Yusuf Kadirov, our only Paralympic athlete, began to honor Uzbekistan by participating in powerlifting and becoming a participant of the Athens 2004 Paralympic sports games. , after the establishment of the Paralympic Association of Uzbekistan in 2007, at the 2008 Paralympic Games held in Beijing, the capital of China, that is, at the Beijing-2008 Paralympic Sports Games, the delegation of Uzbekistan participated in 2 sports (powerlifting and swimming from sports) participated with two athletes.

It would not be an exaggeration to say that the era of winning streaks for our country's athletes has begun since the 2012 Paralympic Games held in London.

10 athletes from our representatives took part in 4 sports at the London-2012 Paralympic Games, and Sharif Khalilov won 1 silver medal in judo in the weight category up to 73 kilograms. This silver medal was the first achievement of our Uzbek Paralympic athletes at the Paralympic sports competitions, and it was written in golden letters in the history of Uzbekistan. The delegation of Uzbekistan took the 67th place in the standings of the London 2012 Paralympic Games with one silver medal.

In 2016, 32 of our athletes from 8 sports took part in the XXXII Summer Paralympic Games in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. won 8 gold, 6 silver and 17 bronze medals and took 16th place overall in the tournament table and ranked first among the Central Asian countries and second among the CIS countries

(Ukraine took 1st place with 171 athletes), 2nd place among Asian countries (after China with 326 athletes).

At the Rio-2016 Paralympic Games, our paraju-do athletes took first place in the overall team in the sport of Ju-do. The most gratifying thing is that our athletes won 6 world, 7 Paralympic and 12 Asian records at the Rio 2016 Paralympic Games.

48 athletes with 55 tickets participated in the Tokyo-2020 XVI Paralympic Sports Games of the Uzbekistan delegation. 17 of our para-athletics athletes with 19 tickets, 7 of our Paralympians in swimming with 12 tickets, 3 of our Para-canoe athletes with 3 tickets, one of our Paralympians in shooting sports 1 athlete with 1 ticket. 12 of our Paraju athletes defended the honor of our country with 12 medals, 2 of our paracademic rowing athletes with 2 medals, 3 athletes of Parapowerlifting with 3 medals.

According to the final results, Uzbek Paralympians won 8 gold,

Having won 6 silver and 5 bronze medals, occupying 16th place in the overall ranking of the tournament, with this figure, athletes of our country are ahead of the Asian teams (after China, Japan and Iran) and the CIS (Russia, Ukraine and (after Azerbaijan) took the fourth place among the countries, and the first place among the Central Asian and Turkic nations.

Our athletes from Surkhandarya, who are leaving an indelible mark in the history of Paralympic sports competitions, who, among the athletes from Uzbekistan, who protect the honor of our country and contribute to the recognition of our country in the world, are showing their careful preparation in sports competitions in world arenas.

We would like to recognize the bronze medalists of the Rio-2016 Paralympic Games in athletics, Hamraev Fakhriddin, and Bozorov Ahror, in powerlifting. Another athlete (athlete) Mirzaqulov Farrukh became a participant of the Rio 2016 Paralympic Sports Games.

The fact that our daughter Naimova Guljanoy from Surkhandarya won a gold medal in the Taekwondo WTF type of sports at the 16th Paralympic Games in Tokyo-2020 is a real sign of courage. And Khurramova Lobar became a participant in the sport of Ju-do at the 2020 Tokyo XVI Paralympic Sports Games.

To date, 5 athletes from Surkhandarya have participated in the history of Paralympic sports competitions, 1 of them was awarded first and 2 were awarded with bronze medals.

Of course, these results did not happen by themselves, for this, the reforms carried out by our state and the conditions created in this regard are of particular importance. The implementation of positive decisions, such as the glorification of the human factor and comprehensive support in the adopted normative documents, inspires our athletes to achieve great achievements.

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